

A SURVEY OF ACADEMIC STAFF PRODUCTIVITY IN SELECTED UNIVERSITIES IN SOUTHWEST, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the academic staff productivity in selected universities in South-West, Nigeria. The study employed the descriptive research design of the correlational type. Data for the study was done using a structured questionnaire. Data analysis was done descriptively with the Relative Importance Index (RII) approach as well as multiple regression analysis. The study revealed that the RII of all the items were greater than the threshold of 0.5. The findings revealed an overall high level of staff productivity in the selected universities, except for one of the items which are less than 0.5. Furthermore, the analysis revealed that published paper assessment ($\beta = 0.779$, $t = 3.850$, $p < 0.5$), community service ($\beta = 0.656$, $t = 3.025$, $p < 0.5$) and new curricula designed and developed ($\beta = 0.793$, $t = 3.876$, $p < 0.5$) significantly predicted academic staff productivity, while, general performance appraisal ($\beta = -1.236$, $t = -5.080$, $p > 0.5$), project evaluation appraisal ($\beta = -0.463$, $t = -1.820$, $p > 0.5$), employee self-assessment appraisal ($\beta = -0.066$, $t = -0.312$, $p > 0.5$), teaching ($\beta = -1.222$, $t = -5.856$, $p > 0.5$), research ($\beta = 0.410$, $t = -1.795$, $p > 0.5$), research, teaching and community service ($\beta = -1.517$, $t = -6.721$, $p > 0.5$), advisory and counsel service ($\beta = -0.578$, $t = -2.611$, $p > 0.5$), success in general external funding to support research or other program ($\beta = -0.806$, $t = -3.196$, $p < 0.5$) and attraction of research grants ($\beta = 0.335$, $t = 1.387$, $p < 0.5$) did not significantly predict academic staff productivity in these selected universities in South West Nigeria. The study concluded that performance appraisal has a significant relationship with academic staff productivity in South-West, Nigeria and that productivity of the academic staff is determined by the extent of performance appraisal system in use in the various universities in South-West, Nigeria.

Keywords: Academic staff, Productivity, Universities, Southwest, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Productivity is a product of conscious actions set by an organization to achieve specific set goals. Academic productivity is critical and of utmost importance to the existence, growth and competitive advantage of any university in the world and specifically, Nigeria. While Universities need academic staff to get the job done, how well it is done affects a whole lot with regards to student recruitment, positive ranking and ability to secure funds, general reputation, as well as attraction and retention of top-notch lecturers. One must also add that productivity here would directly impact the fiscal posture of a university, through increased revenue from more subscription to its programmes by students. Invariably, the need for enhanced productivity necessitates the quest for performance appraisal.

Whether a university or any other organization, performance appraisal is a part of the management system that starts with the recruitment of trainable staff (Mwema, & Gachunga, 2014) and continues to include efforts to ensure suitability for promotion, training and periodic evaluation of employee's performance measured against the job's stated requirements. It is a form of human resource management that enables the employer to assess the performance of the employee to give guidelines or advice for improving the organization's efficiency and effectiveness (Hughes, 2018; Bernardine and Russel, 2013; Terry and Franklin, 2003). In Nigeria, just as obtained in the other climes, the university has standard criteria for the recruitment of academic staff as the staff needs of a university is provided for, chiefly by the National Universities Commission's requirement as stated in their rules. What is critical to this process remains the identification of the tools and strategies for performance appraisal and the variation in the application of the same tools from university to university and largely based on the nature of the ownership and general objectives and challenges of the university.

While organisations may differ in scope, purpose, nature and line of business, the central concern of performance appraisal is productivity-driven through the conduits of efficiency, effectiveness and competence and is usually carried out systematically and periodical (Omojola, 2019; DeNisi and Pritchard 2006). Within this frame, appraisals may help poor employees improve performance by giving specific feedback about development needs and also assist employees who continue to excel by giving positive reinforcement (Mani, 2002). This type of feedback is essential to improve the performance of employees at all levels and to assess the accomplishments of the organization's goal. In the University system, once productivity is the hallmark, appraisal remains one of the criteria in decisions to retain employees during layoffs, assess the quality of training programs, measure the equitable treatment of different groups of employees, increase employees' pay, and promote or terminate employees' job in the organization (Gabris and Ihrke, 2001).

At the inception of private universities, productivity was at the core as they were of critical concern to varying challenges of survival, growth and progressive recruitment of students. As such, they were concerned with more direct students'

feedback by developing some direct scales of appraisal of academic staff productivity. Generally, Academic staff productivity had, before now, been exclusively limited to the domain of the three core areas that have a direct impact on the career of academic staff. These are research, teaching and community service. Performance appraisal at this point and in the universities over time has been on the interplay of administrative checks that is natural to the university system and which include the checks and scales of measurement of the trio of research, teaching and community service as the right bundle for consideration for the reward which usually comes as a promotion. From the inception of universities up till 1999, performance appraisal was pitched on, administrative, motivational, development and performance improvement purposes (Igbojekwe, and Ugo-Okoro, 2015).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Productivity is at the core of any business private or the public world over. To operate within the frame of productivity, businesses and institutions periodically embark on performance appraisal to measure attainment to set goals based on staff specific input and/or standard deviation from same. Universities are unique industry players, given that they are both the centres of learning as well as large labour field whose acts itself contributes to learning outcome and standards. This research work surveyed academic staff productivity in selected universities in the South-west

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this research is to examine the productivity of academic staff of selected universities in South-Western Nigeria. Specifically, the study examined the extent to which performance appraisal influences academic staff productivity in the selected universities in South-West Nigeria.

Research questions

To what extent has performance appraisal influenced academic staff productivity in the selected universities in South-West Nigeria?

Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis was tested at a 0.05 level of significance
H₀1: There is a significant influence of performance appraisal on academic staff productivity in universities in South West, Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Academic Staff Productivity

First, Productivity is the effective and efficient use of all resources which include time, people, knowledge, information, finance, equipment, energy and materials. Productivity is the ratio of output to input and it is a measure of how a business or an economy uses inputs such as labour and capital to produce outputs or goods and services (Adedayo, 2017). Productivity is the ratio of what

is produced and what is required to produce it. According to Broman (2004), one of the major concerns of the organization is improving worker's productivity which implies the level or degree of output (sales, earnings, and market share) achieved from a defined input (material/equipment costs, labour hours or production costs) and that employee's knowledge, skills, abilities, attitude, motivation and behaviours affect productivity. Prokepenko (1996) defined productivity as the relationship between the output generated by a production or service system and the input provided to create this output. It may also include a range of human activity, from handicraft to high tech in which raw materials are transformed into finished goods on a large scale (Allmon, Haas, Borchering and Goodrum 2000). Productivity is, therefore, closely connected to the use and availability of resources.

Productivity is the state of achieving institutional goals and objectives by transforming inputs (human, financial and material resources) into outputs (services or service delivery tangibles) at the lowest cost (Bhatti and Qureshi, 2007; Robbins and Judge, 2011). The definition of productivity contains key elements which include continuous improvement of performance, measurability of improvement, efficiency and effectiveness (Adedayo, 2017). Gust and Marquez (2004) asserts that the growth rate of labour productivity is approximately equal to the difference between the growth rate of output and the growth rate of the number of hours worked in the economy. In essence, productivity is the output of goods and services per unit of resources used in the production process or optimizing employee outputs to the goals of the organization by managing talents and abilities together with job environment and employee morale. This is also in line with the position of Eleine, Hailey and Kelliher, (2010) that employee productivity is the process by which executives, managers and supervisors work to align employee performance to the firm's goals. In other words, it is a means of getting better results for the organization.

Academic productivity is the rate at which lecturers achieve individual given objectives about the institution goal achievement. The level of lecturer's productivity differs from one lecturer to another. These differences may not be connected to the motivating factors use in the university ranging from welfare scheme, health scheme and promotion or performance appraisal (Abdulkareem, 2015). Also, lecturers undergo higher education qualification programmes and published in accredited journals, textbooks, articles, documents and service to the community as these provide the basis for promotion to a higher level in the service. Thus when a lecturer's skills are developed through various programmes, like seminars, workshops, mentoring, further education, induction courses and establishment of adequate reference libraries, their productivity is enhanced, as well as that of the institutions. In addition to personal development, Adeyemi (2010) states that academic productivity can be measured in terms of teaching, lesson preparation, mastery of subject matter, commitment to job and extracurricular activities, effective supervision and monitoring of student's work, class control and disciplinary ability.

Astin and Lee reveal (1967) that academic staff roles involved classroom teaching and research and supporting, sustaining, developing and promoting innovation in society. Centra (1977) support the position that academic staff roles include community and public service, advising students and service to the institution. Hassna and Raza (2011) identified three roles of academic staff productivity; teaching, scholarly endeavours; and service to the university. This role implies that academic staff carried out teaching and supervision, research and innovation, publication, consultancy and services. Iqbal, Rasli and Heng (2011) aver that academic staff produced development solutions through innovations in terms of designing relevant programmes and courses, teaching, examination and supervision of students' research. Mawoli and Babandako (2013) are in support of this position that academic staff productivity is in terms of attendance teaching, research and publications.

Majasan, (1998) maintained that academic productivity is value-loaded and produced disciplined behaviour, hard work, improved cultural heritage and mutual respect within and outside the school community. Okebukola (2004) thinks that academic productivity is a process of continuous improvement in the quality of teaching and learning activities through the employment of mechanisms, internal and external to the institution, such that the provision of minimum academic standards documents is attained maintained and enhanced. Academic productivity could be measured by how well a university has prepared for life and service to society in various spheres of human endeavour.

Oslow (2007) attest to the view that academic productivity is a reflection of the performance of graduates in the labour market which is also dependent on the quality of academic programmes and provision of infrastructural facilities. Apart from employing qualified academic staff, they must be well-trained while on the job. Babalola (2006) assert that the output indicators for measuring university education include the qualifications and levels of competence in the performance of the outputs (students) using the knowledge and skill acquired. Also, the effective performance of the outputs in the job competitive market, their impact on moral conduct and serviceability on the society are indicators for measuring academic productivity (Centra, 1977). Archibong and Okey (2006) states that academic productivity is a process of recognizing educational institutions for an excellent level of performance, integrity and quality which enables them to gain the confidence of the educational community, the public they serve and the employers of labour. Continuous improvement in the quality of teaching and learning activities is achieved through accreditation exercise which involves internal and external mechanism (Fapohunda, 2015).

According to Ajayi (2007), academic productivity may include evaluation of instructional delivery, adequacy of facilities and equipment, standardized tests analysis of theses and recitals completion rates, results of admission test for students applying to graduate or professional schools, job placement rates, the result of licensing examinations evaluation by employers, follow up studies of alumni and performance of student transfers at receiving institutions. These factors are broadly grouped into five namely, academic content, management,

physical facilities, equipment and funding (Archibong and Okey, 2006). Okebukola (2008) categorized educational resources into human, material, physical and financial, and explains them further as follows.

Human resources in education include students, teaching staff, non-teaching staff, bursar, librarian, laboratory attendants, clerks, messengers, mail runners, gatekeepers, gardeners and cooks as well as educational planners and administrators.

- i. Material resources include textbooks, charts, and maps, audio-visual and electronic instructional materials such as radio, tape recorder, television and videotape recorder. Other categories of material resources are paper supplies and writing materials such as biro, eraser, exercise books, crayon, chalk, drawing books, notebooks, pencil, ruler, slate, workbooks among others.
- ii. Physical resources include classrooms, lecture theatres, auditoriums, typing pools, administrative block, libraries, laboratories, workshops, gymnasia, assembly halls, special rooms like sickbay, staff quarters, students 'hostels, kitchen, cafeteria, lavatory and toilet.
- iii. Financial resources are the monetary inputs available for and expended on the education system. These include money allocated to education by the government such as grants and donations from philanthropists, alumnus and internally generated funds.

The performance of a lecturer refers to how he undertakes the professional duties in the school at a given time. Robbins, Odendaal and Roodt (2007) outlined seven performance dimensions of an academic job as knowledge (subject knowledge); testing (assessment) procedures; student-teacher relations; organizational skills; communication skills; subject relevance and utility of assignments. Shulman (1987) elaborated on the knowledge bases needed for effective teaching to include content knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge of education ends, purposes and values, curriculum knowledge including materials and programmes, knowledge of learners and their characteristics, knowledge of educational contexts including characteristics of classrooms, schools, communities and cultures and general pedagogical knowledge including principles and strategies for classroom management and organization. Adeyemi (2010) reaffirm this position that a teacher's performance can be measure in terms of teaching, lesson preparation, mastery of subject matter, commitment to the job and extra-curricular activities, effective supervision and monitoring of student's work, class control and disciplinary ability. Therefore, an assessment of a lecturer's job performance must be based on specified academic duties that improve the skills of lecturers and the students.

The most consistent view that can be drawn from the different perspectives of performance appraisal remains the fact, that performance appraisal has to do with mechanisms, structures and systems developed by an organisation to track standard alignment to organisational objectives and service delivery by its workforce to gauge standard deviation from organisational set

goals. It goes from being a mere organizational routine to a culture that defines the values of an organisation as well as standard it out to be goal-oriented. It can be deducted that once trainable staff are employed, organizational goals and missions are well mapped out, performance appraisal becomes a familiar terrain that will always yield an expected result of productivity. In the university system, while the three most defining aspects of performance appraisal have remained on the front burner in most literature reviewed here, in praxis, most private, federal and state universities have gone beyond these routines to expand their understanding of performance to feedback from students and parents as core stakeholders that has the most pronounced impact on the sustainability of a university body through continued patronage.

METHODOLOGY

This research work is descriptive in nature and a survey design method has been adopted to collect data from the sample that is drawn from a study population of Five thousand, three hundred and fifty-two (5,352) academic staff. The target population for this study consisted of all categories of academic staff in the following universities in South-West Nigeria: University of Ibadan (UI), Ladoke Akintola University of Technology, Ogbomoso (LAUTECH), Lead City University, Ibadan (all in Oyo State); Federal University of Agriculture Abeokuta (FUNAAB), Olabisi Onabanjo University, Ago-Iwoye (OOU), Babcock University Ilesan-Remo (BU) (all in Ogun State); Obafemi Awolowo University Ile-Ife (OAU), Osun State University (UNIOSUN), Oduduwa University Ipetumodu (OUI) (all in Osun State). A 99% confidence level with a margin of error (degree of accuracy) of 3.5% was adopted in determining the sample size for this study, resulting in a sample size of 1011 from a population of 5352. This study involves the use of both stratified and purposive sampling techniques. Given this, the universities were purposively selected and stratified into Federal, State and Private universities. The main data collection instrument was a structured questionnaire. Primary data was collected through the structured questionnaire as well as interviews. Secondary data was derived from relevant textbooks, journals, periodicals, newspapers, magazines, seminar papers, archives, government and international organization publications, documentary and records, internet and other related materials. The data collected for the study was analysed descriptively with the Relative Importance Index (RII) approach as well as multiple regression analysis. The relative importance index helps to rank the criteria according to their relative importance. The following formula is used to determine the relative index.

$$R.I = \frac{W_A}{N} \quad \text{or} \quad RII = \frac{\text{Sum of weights } W_1 + W_2 + W_3 \dots + W_n}{N}$$

$$R.I. = \text{or } RII$$

Where:

W is the weighting as assigned by each respondent on a scale of one to five, with one implying the least and five the highest.

A is the highest weight and

N is the total number of the sample. Based on the ranking (R) of the Relative Importance Index (RII), the weighted average of the two groups will be determined. According to Akadiri (2011), five important levels are transformed from (RII) values: H (H) ($0.74 \leq RII$), High-Medium (H-M) ($0.69 \leq RII \leq 1$) and low (L) ($0.59 \leq RII \leq 1$).

RESULTS

Research 1: To what extent has performance appraisal influenced academic staff productivity in the selected universities in South-West Nigeria?

Table 1: Extent academic staff productivity in the selected universities in South-West Nigeria

	Productivity items	N	Mean	Std. Dev	RII	Ranking
1	Community student	1011	3.08	1.20	0.616	1 st
2	Improved student academic performance	1011	2.98	1.11	0.597	2 nd
3	Skill acquisition and entrepreneurship	1011	2.91	1.10	0.582	3 rd
4	Research/publications	1011	2.75	1.16	0.550	4 th
5	Supervision of student	1011	2.65	1.04	0.530	5 th
6	Teaching	1011	2.49	0.94	0.498	6 th

Source: filed survey 2021

Table 1, revealed that the RII of all the items were greater than the threshold of 0.5 and hence it implies a high level of staff productivity in the selected universities, except one of the items which are less than 0.5, and therefore is not significant. Community students accounted for the largest RII (0.616), this was closely followed by improved student academic performance (0.597), skill acquisition and entrepreneurship (0.582), research/publications (0.550) and supervision of student (0.530) while the only item which isn't significant according to the study is teaching (0.498).

Testing of hypothesis

H₀1: There is a significant influence of performance appraisal on academic staff productivity in universities in South West, Nigeria.

Table 2: Regression analysis showing the influence of performance appraisal on academic staff productivity in universities in South West, Nigeria.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.569 ^a	.324	.316	4.48492

ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	9605.395	12	800.450	39.795	.000 ^b
1 Residual	20074.311	998	20.115		
Total	29679.705	1010			

a. Dependent Variable: Productivity

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
(Constant)	29.662	.685			43.331	.000
General performance appraisal	-1.236	.243	-.217		-5.080	.000
Project evaluation appraisal	-.463	.255	-.076		-1.820	.069
Employee self-assessment appraisal	-.066	.210	-.013		-.312	.755
Published paper assessment	.779	.202	.163		3.850	.000
Teaching	-1.222	.209	-.239		-5.856	.000
Community Service	.656	.217	.138		3.025	.003
Research	-.410	.229	-.076		-1.795	.073
Research, teaching and community service	-1.517	.226	-.282		-6.721	.000
New curricula designed and developed	.793	.205	.153		3.867	.000
Advisory and counsel service	-.578	.221	-.107		-2.611	.009
success in general external funding to support research or other program	-.806	.252	-.164		-3.196	.001
Attraction of research grants	.335	.241	.071		1.387	.166

Dependent Variable: Productivity

Table 2 shows that the model accounted for 32.4% of variation in the dependent variable (productivity). When it comes to how well the regression equation fits the data, the table indicated that the regression model predicts the dependent variable significantly well ($F_{(12,39.7)} = 39.795$, $p < 0.5$) indicating a significant relationship between performance appraisal and academic staff productivity. Furthermore, the analysis revealed that published paper assessment ($\beta = 0.779$, $t = 3.850$, $p < 0.5$), community service ($\beta = 0.656$, $t = 3.025$, $p < 0.5$) and new

curricula designed and developed ($\beta = 0.793$, $t = 3.876$, $p < 0.5$) significantly predicted academic staff productivity, while, general performance appraisal ($\beta = -1.236$, $t = -5.080$, $p > 0.5$), project evaluation appraisal ($\beta = -0.463$, $t = -1.820$, $p > 0.5$), employee self-assessment appraisal ($\beta = -0.066$, $t = -0.312$, $p > 0.5$), teaching ($\beta = -1.222$, $t = -5.856$, $p > 0.5$), research ($\beta = 0.410$, $t = -1.795$, $p > 0.5$), research, teaching and community service ($\beta = -1.517$, $t = -6.721$, $p > 0.5$), advisory and counsel service ($\beta = -0.578$, $t = -2.611$, $p > 0.5$), success in general external funding to support research or other program ($\beta = -0.806$, $t = -3.196$, $p < 0.5$) and attraction of research grants ($\beta = 0.335$, $t = 1.387$, $p < 0.5$) did not significantly predict academic staff productivity in these selected universities in South West Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

Findings from this study revealed an overall high level of staff productivity in the selected universities, except one of the items which are less than 0.5, and therefore is not significant; besides, the study concluded that performance appraisal has a significant relationship with academic staff productivity in South-West, Nigeria. This implies that the productivity of the academic staff is determined by the extent of the performance appraisal system in use in the various universities in South-West, Nigeria.

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